

COMPOSITE FORMS OF DEVELOPING THE MOTIVATION OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Motives give a certain direction for activity and keep a person within this path. In the field of physical education and sports, motivation is considered from a specific position. The article examines the internal and external structural forms of the development of students' motivation during physical training.*

Keywords: *motive, activity, need, exercise, sport, activity, activity, action, goal, freedom, reflex, competition, competition.*

In the field of physical education and sports, motivation is considered from a specific position. Internal and external structural forms of development of students' motivation during physical education training are components of the definition of motivation.

Motivation is the main variable in the acquisition of physical education and sports skills, in the ability to demonstrate them [1, p. 45].

Motivation is, first of all, a desire for success, high results in one's work. If a person strives for success, to achieve high results in activities, then it is a sign that he has a strong enough success motivation [1, p. 56].

The main psychological feature of the motivations that motivate a person to engage in physical education and sports is the feeling of inseparable satisfaction from playing sports and the sports activity itself. At the same time, these motives have a complex nature according to the complexity and variety of physical education and sports activities, and they can be divided into:

- 1) motives of direct physical education and sports activities:
 - a) the athlete's unique feeling of satisfaction from the manifestation of muscle activity;
 - b) aesthetic enjoyment of the beauty, precision, dexterity of their movements;
 - c) the desire to prove oneself with courage and determination in performing difficult and dangerous exercises;
 - d) satisfaction from participation in the competition, which is considered the most important and mandatory aspect of sports;
 - e) achieving record results, proving one's sportsmanship, the desire to win, no matter how difficult it may be, etc.
- 2) Indirect motives of physical education and sports activities:
 - a) striving to be strong, energetic, healthy ("I play sports because it improves health and makes a person happy and energetic");
 - b) striving to prepare oneself for practical training through physical education and sports ("I do sports because I want to be physically stronger");
 - v) understanding the social importance of physical education and sports activities ("I want to win world records, defend the sports flag of my country") [1, p. 14-20].

Currently, there are three theories that explain what motivates (induces) a person to action:

- 1) the theory of the need for success;

- 2) attribute theory,
- 3) the theory of goal attainment.

From the analysis of literary sources devoted to the problem of physical education and motivation to engage in sports, it is clear that the motivation that encourages a person to engage in sports occupies a special place in the psychological provision of sports activities [2, p. 54]. The motivation block is formed by the needs, motives and goals of physical education and sports activities.

A need, or a person's feeling of needing something, indicates a disproportion with the environment. Psychologically, this is always associated with the appearance of internal tension, more or less obvious discomfort, which can be eliminated only by satisfying the corresponding need. That's why any need evokes the so-called search activity, aimed at finding a way to satisfy it. Research by scientists shows that any need can be satisfied in different ways. A person can choose any method from what he knows, but in fact his range of choices is limited by the specific conditions of life. Sometimes the circumstances of life itself push you to choose a certain path. And then the choice happens by itself, without a clear understanding of the process. Most of the time, there is a choice of sports activities as a way to satisfy the first, perhaps only one, and then the entire needs.

G.D. Gorbunov includes the following needs in this complex: the need for activity, activity, movement, the need to realize goals and freedom reflexes, competition, competition, the need for self-affirmation, grouping, communication, the need for new experiences, etc. [3].

A motive is an incentive to a certain activity, to satisfy a need in a certain way. If the need is the source of activity, then motives give a certain direction to this activity and keep a person within this path. Motives make it possible to understand why certain goals are set, an unquenchable desire to achieve them appears. Sports activities are characterized by various motives. This can be explained by physical and mental stress, and a person should know what he is spending himself on [3].

It should be noted that the unsatisfaction of the problem of motivation in the development of students' motivation during physical education training, the lack of unity and accuracy in determining the essence of this phenomenon leaves its mark on the methodological approaches to the study of motives. For successful student-athletes, it is recommended to give them a difficult but doable task. Because they prefer to take intermediate risks and perform better in evaluated situations, the trainer is advised to create such conditions during training. A different approach is necessary for a student-athlete who has not achieved great success: it is recommended to direct the athlete to the task, choose average or real tasks.

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